

Energy and Exergy Analysis of Vapour Compression Refrigeration System with Low-GWP Based Nanorefrigerant

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ABSTRACT

Vapour compression refrigeration cycle is the most widely used thermodynamic cycle in refrigerators and air conditioners. Poor thermophysical properties of conventional refrigerants can be improved by dispersing nanoparticles into pure refrigerant and thereby preparing a distinct variety of working fluid, namely nanorefrigerant. This paper theoretically investigates the performance of Al₂O₃/ R600a nanorefrigerant in vapour compression refrigeration cycle. A mathematical model is developed in 'Engineering Equation Solver (EES)' to study the energetic and exergetic aspects of the cycle operating with nanorefrigerant of varying mass fractions. Results indicate that both COP and cooling capacity increase with the addition of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles. Compared to pure R600a, nanorefrigerant delivers a higher COP, except at very high evaporator temperatures. The study also reveals a reduction in total exergy destruction and increase in exergy efficiency for selected cycle temperatures. These findings underline the ability of nanorefrigerants to enhance the efficiency and environmental sustainability of refrigeration systems.

KEYWORDS: *Nanorefrigerant, VCRC, Exergy, Low-GWP, COP, Nanoparticles*

1 INTRODUCTION

Global energy crisis demands for highly energy efficient and environment-friendly system. Refrigeration and air conditioning (RAC) sector, which consumes nearly 17% of the global electricity production and also responsible for approximately 8% of the total greenhouse gas emissions (Salehy et al., 2020), needs to be addressed for actively contributing towards achieving the United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In order to attain a higher efficiency of the existing RAC systems, the thermal characteristics of conventional refrigerants must be improved. Nanorefrigerant is relatively a new kind of working fluid where nanoparticles of metals or metal oxides of size 1-100 nm are dispersed to a base of pure conventional refrigerant. Nanoparticles can notably improve the thermophysical properties of the base refrigerant leading to a better overall performance and lesser energy consumption.

Sajid and Ali (2018) in their review work showed how thermal conductivity of the refrigerant is enhanced by adding different nanoparticles into it. Javadi et al. (2021) experimentally demonstrated that the addition of 0.1% Al₂O₃ nanoparticles into R134a resulted in reduction of energy consumption by approximately 2.69%. In another experiment on ice plant test rig, Dhamneya et al. (2018) showed that coefficient of performance (COP) of vapour compression refrigeration cycle (VCRC) increased by 51% when they used TiO₂/R134a nanorefrigerant in place of pure R134a. Javadi and Saidur (2013) calculated that the use of 0.1% TiO₂-mineral oil-R134a nanorefrigerant caused a maximum energy saving of 25% when was compared with a few other nanorefrigerants. In their study on Al₂O₃/R134a nanorefrigerant, Mahbulul et al. (2015) analysed the effect of nanoparticles on thermophysical properties of base refrigerant and also on COP of the system. Alawi et al. (2019) conducted a similar kind of study, where they reported enhancements in key thermo-physical properties of the Al₂O₃/R-141b nano-refrigerant. Specifically, the density, dynamic viscosity, and thermal conductivity improved by approximately 11.54%, 12.63%, and 28.88%, respectively. Mahdi et al. (2017) operated an experiment on a double pipe counter flow heat exchanger using two different concentrations of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles dispersed in R134a. They showed that compressor power consumption was decreased by 1.6% and 3.3% for nanoparticle volume fractions of 0.0001 and 0.0002 respectively. It is apparent from the previous studies that addition of nanoparticles results in better thermophysical properties such as enhanced thermal conductivity and specific heat, which leads to improved performance of refrigeration

cycle. On the other hand, dispersion of nanoparticles increases density and viscosity of the base refrigerant (Dey and Mandal, 2020), resulting in higher pressure drop and more pumping power requirements (Yang et al., 2015). Since, refrigerant in VCRC undergoes phase changing process in evaporator and condenser, the overall performance is highly affected by the boiling and condensation heat transfer properties of the refrigerant. There are several studies on nanofluid pool boiling (Ham and Cho, 2016, Norouzipour et al., 2019, Ali et al., 2017), which primarily focuses on investigating the effect of nanoparticles on critical heat flux and boiling heat transfer coefficient. Whereas, only a few studies (Tazari et al., 2016, Baqeri et al., 2014, Henderson et al., 2015, Dey and Mandal 2021) have been conducted on nanorefrigerant flow boiling characteristics.

To verify the performance of any vapour compression refrigeration system, one generally evaluates coefficient of performance (COP), compressor power and cooling capacity among other parameters. In addition to that, exergy analysis is an effective tool for identifying irreversibility in refrigeration cycles and assessing the system's scope for improvement. Li and Lu (2022) performed a theoretical study on the effect of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles in four different base refrigerants in VCRC. They reported a highest exergy efficiency of 38.46% for R1233zd(E) + 0.3% Al_2O_3 nanorefrigerant. The same combination also delivered the highest COP among others chosen. Aktemur and Öztürk (2022) developed a mathematical model for assessing the performance of booster assisted ejector expansion refrigeration systems with R1270/CuO nano-refrigerant. The authors reported an improvement in exergy efficiency and COP by 9.47% and 9.46% respectively, both corresponding to 2 wt.% CuO. In a recent study, Yilmaz et al. (2024) theoretically analysed the energy, exergy and environmental aspects of R290-R1233ZDE refrigerant with CNT, CuO, and TiO_2 nanoparticles in a cascade VCRC. Among the three, CuO depicted the highest COP and exergy efficiency for 0.05% mass fraction.

Although there are some papers available on nanorefrigerant thermophysical properties and cycle COP investigation, only a few works have been conducted on exergy and energy analysis of nanorefrigerants in VCRC. The gap is basically due to the non-availability of property values of nanorefrigerant at various state points in VCRC. This paper aims to investigate the performance of Alumina (Al_2O_3)/ Isobutane (R600a) nanorefrigerant in VCRC by evaluating the COP and exergy efficiency of the cycle. Other performance parameters such as cooling capacity and total exergy destruction rate of pure refrigerant and nanorefrigerant are also calculated and compared by varying the nanoparticle mass fraction (0.1% - 0.5%). Reason for choosing R600a as the base refrigerant is its zero ODP and a very low GWP value of 3. On the other hand, Al_2O_3 nanoparticles are widely used in nanofluid heat transfer applications and its thermophysical properties are available in literature.

2 MATHEMATICAL MODELLING

Engineering Equation Solver (EES) is a program that can numerically solve a system of algebraic and differential equations. It has inbuilt library of thermodynamic properties of real fluids including refrigerants. EES is used in this work to model the refrigeration system operating with Al_2O_3 /R600a nanorefrigerant.

2.1 VCRC with nanorefrigerant

Figure 1 shows the P-h plot of vapour compression refrigeration cycle where, nanorefrigerant enters compressor at point 1, which is on saturated vapour line, since no superheating is considered in evaporator. Process 1-2 represents the compression process, whose isentropic efficiency is taken as 0.80. Nanorefrigerant leaves the condenser as saturated liquid (point 3) and no sub-cooling is taking place in the condenser. Heat loss and pressure drop of the refrigerant neglected in this study. Moreover, nanoparticles are assumed to be uniformly dispersed in the base refrigerant and no sedimentation is taken into account. Unlike pure refrigerants, nanorefrigerant thermodynamic properties are not defined at various state points. Density of nanorefrigerant can be used as an input to calculate other thermodynamic properties like specific enthalpy and specific entropy as

Figure 1. P-h plot of VCRC

depicted in the works of Aktas et al. (2015), Aktemur and Öztürk (2022), Li and Lu (2022) and Yilmaz et al. (2024). Density of nanorefrigerant (ρ_{nr}) can be calculated from the density of pure refrigerant (ρ_r) and nanoparticle density (ρ_{np}) as (Pak and Cho, 1998):

$$\rho_{nr} = \phi\rho_{np} + (1 - \phi)\rho_r \quad (1)$$

Where, ϕ is the volume fraction of nanoparticles in base refrigerant. Volume fraction of nanoparticles can be correlated to mass fraction (ω) as the following:

$$\phi = \frac{\omega\rho_r}{\omega\rho_r + (1 - \omega)\rho_{np}} \quad (2)$$

Enthalpies (h) of nanorefrigerant at various state points are calculated as described here. First, density of saturated vapour R600a at point 1 is determined from EES library. Then from Eqs. (1) and (2), density of nanorefrigerant is calculated corresponding to point 1. Using the density of nanorefrigerant and evaporator temperature as input parameters, authors have evaluated the enthalpy value at point 1. A similar approach is followed for condenser outlet enthalpy (h_3). Evaporator inlet point has the same value of enthalpy as that of point 3 as the expansion process is isenthalpic. Compressor outlet enthalpy (h_2) is calculated by equating specific entropy (s) of compressor inlet and outlet, taking into account isentropic efficiency of the compression process. Various input parameters needed for the cycle analysis are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Input parameters

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Density of Al ₂ O ₃ (ρ_{np})	3690 kg/m ³	Evaporator temperature (T_e)	-15 to 10 °C
Nanoparticle mass fraction (ω)	0.1% - 0.5%	Condenser temperature (T_c)	35 to 55 °C
Mass flow rate of nanorefrigerant (\dot{m})	0.04458 kg/s	Compressor isentropic efficiency	0.80

Formula for coefficient of performance (COP) of the cycle is no different from that of the basic VCRC, and is given by:

$$COP = \frac{\dot{Q}_L}{\dot{W}_{comp}} = \frac{\dot{m}(h_1 - h_4)}{\dot{m}(h_2 - h_1)} \quad (3)$$

Where \dot{Q}_L and \dot{W}_{comp} are the rate of heat removal from low temperature medium (cooling capacity) and compressor power consumption respectively.

2.2 Exergy analysis

The VCRC is operating between a lower temperature medium at -5°C (T_L) and a high temperature surrounding at 30°C (T_H). Dead state temperature (T_0) for refrigeration cycle is generally the temperature of the surrounding. The maximum COP of a cycle between the two temperature limits is obtained when the cycle totally reversible. Reversible COP (COP_R) between temperatures T_L and T_H is shown by Eq. (4).

$$COP_R = \frac{T_L}{T_H - T_L} \quad (4)$$

Neglecting the kinetic and potential energy changes, exergy destruction (\dot{X}_{dest}) in a component in VCRC can be written in terms of entropy generation (\dot{S}_{gen}) as:

$$\dot{X}_{dest} = T_0\dot{S}_{gen} \quad (5)$$

Exergy destruction for four main components of VCR cycle drawn in Figure 1, may be represented as follows (Kanoğlu et al., 2012):

Compressor

$$\dot{X}_{dest,1-2} = T_0 \dot{S}_{gen,1-2} = \dot{m} T_0 (s_2 - s_1) \tag{6}$$

Condenser

$$\dot{X}_{dest,2-3} = T_0 \dot{S}_{gen,2-3} = T_0 [\dot{m}(s_3 - s_2) + \frac{\dot{Q}_H}{T_H}] \tag{7}$$

Expansion valve

$$\dot{X}_{dest,3-4} = T_0 \dot{S}_{gen,3-4} = \dot{m} T_0 (s_4 - s_3) \tag{8}$$

Evaporator

$$\dot{X}_{dest,4-1} = T_0 \dot{S}_{gen,4-1} = T_0 [\dot{m}(s_1 - s_4) - \frac{\dot{Q}_L}{T_L}] \tag{9}$$

Total exergy destruction of the cycle is the sum of exergy destruction of each component as depicted in Eq. (10).

$$\dot{X}_{dest,total} = \dot{X}_{dest,1-2} + \dot{X}_{dest,2-3} + \dot{X}_{dest,3-4} + \dot{X}_{dest,4-1} \tag{10}$$

Second law efficiency or exergy efficiency of the VCRC is expressed as

$$\epsilon_{cycle} = \frac{\dot{X}_{QL}}{\dot{W}_{in}} = \frac{\dot{Q}_L(T_0 - T_L)/T_L}{\dot{Q}_L/COP_R} = \frac{COP}{T_L/(T_H - T_L)} = \frac{COP}{COP_R} \tag{11}$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Performance analysis with varying mass fraction

COP and cooling capacity of refrigerator are two main parameters for analysing performance of a VCRC. As the mass fraction of Al₂O₃ nanoparticle is increased from 0.1 % to 0.5%, both COP and cooling capacity increases almost linearly as depicted in Figure 2 and 3. Starting from 2.876, which the COP value for pure R600a, cycle COP increases to 4.5 corresponding to 0.5% mass fraction of nanoparticles. Cooling capacity of the cycle when pure R600a is used is represented by 0% mass fraction in Figure 3. The maximum cooling capacity obtained is 15.7 kW (0.5% mass fraction) compared to 10.34 kW for pure refrigerant. Enhanced evaporator cooling reduces the compressor power requirement and reduces the size of the refrigerator for same cooling capacity. This improvement in

Figure 2. Variation of COP with mass fraction

Figure 3. Variation of cooling capacity with mass fraction

performance is mainly attributed to the better thermophysical properties like thermal conductivity and heat transfer coefficient of nanorefrigerant.

COP of VCRC generally increases with decreasing temperature difference between evaporator and condenser, i.e. with increasing evaporator temperature and decreasing condenser temperature. VCRC with nanorefrigerant is no different as clear from Figure 4 and 5. It can be seen from Figure 4 that COP of Al₂O₃/R600a nanorefrigerant is almost always higher than that of pure R600a, except for evaporator temperatures higher than 5°C. Thus, nanorefrigerant is showing better thermal performance for lower evaporator temperatures. Whereas for the whole condenser temperature range of 35-55°C,

Figure 4. Effect of evaporator temperature on COP

Figure 5. Effect of condenser temperature on COP

nanorefrigerant with 0.3% mass fraction of Al₂O₃ offering higher COP. Moreover, Al₂O₃/R600a is less sensitive to cycle temperature changes as compared to pure R600a in the given temperature ranges.

3.2 Exergy analysis

Exergy is the potential of a system to do useful work. Exergy analysis helps to identify irreversibility in processes and systems providing an insight into how far a system is from reversible one. Figure 6 shows the effect of nanoparticles on total exergy destruction rate of the cycle. It can be observed that addition of nanoparticles decreases the total exergy destruction. For instance, pure R600a is responsible for total exergy destruction of 2.245 kW. Whereas, the lowest exergy destruction of 1.438 kW is achieved by nanoparticles of mass fraction 0.5%.

Total exergy destruction of the cycle for both pure R600a and nanorefrigerant decreases with increasing evaporator temperature when, condenser temperature is made fixed at 45°C as shown in Figure 7. Below -7°C, exergy destruction of Al₂O₃/R600a with $\omega = 0.002$ is lower than that of pure refrigerant. Figure 8 displays the variation of total exergy destruction with condenser temperature when evaporator temperature was fixed at -10°C. Beyond 43°C, exergy destruction of Al₂O₃/R600a becomes lower than that of pure refrigerant making the nanorefrigerant more suitable for high condenser temperatures. Maximum amount of exergy destroyed for pure R600a at 55°C is 2.914 kW whereas for nanorefrigerant the corresponding value is 2.18 kW.

Exergy efficiency or second law efficiency provides a more general metric for comparing different energy systems. The better the exergy efficiency, the better the system utilising available work. Figure 9 and 10 compares the exergy efficiency of pure refrigerant and nanorefrigerant by varying evaporator

Figure 6. Total exergy destruction as a function of nanoparticle mass fraction

and condenser temperature keeping mass fraction constant at 0.2%. For evaporator temperatures lower than 0°C exergy efficiency of Al₂O₃/R600a exceeds the exergy efficiency of pure refrigerant. It can be seen from Figure 9 that for an evaporator temperature of -15°C, pure R600a results in exergy efficiency of 32.83%, while nanorefrigerant shows an exergy efficiency of 43.4%. At almost all temperatures in the selected range of condenser temperature in Figure 10, Al₂O₃/R600a surpasses pure refrigerant in terms of exergy efficiency. At 55°C, when the exergy efficiency of pure refrigerant falls down to 29.12%, the exergy efficiency of nanorefrigerant is calculated to be 41.83%. This clearly justifies the use of Al₂O₃/R600a in place of pure R600a.

Figure 7. Effect of evaporator temperature on total exergy destruction

Figure 8. Effect of condenser temperature on total exergy destruction

Figure 9. Variation of exergy efficiency with evaporator temperature

Figure 10. Variation of exergy efficiency with condenser temperature

4. CONCLUSIONS

Thermodynamic modelling of VCRC is done for energetic and exergetic analysis of Al₂O₃/R600a. Density of nanorefrigerant is used as an input property to calculate the enthalpy at various state points. Effect of nanoparticle mass fraction and cycle temperatures on COP, evaporator cooling rate, exergy destruction and exergy efficiency are analysed. The main conclusions of this study are as follows:

- COP of the cycle increased by 56% when Al₂O₃ nanoparticles with mass fraction 0.005 is added to pure R600a. Cooling capacity i.e. rate of heat removal in the evaporator is increased by almost 52% after addition of 0.5% nanoparticles by mass.
- Cycle COP with nanorefrigerant remains higher than that of pure R600a for lower evaporator temperatures. As most domestic and industrial VCR systems have evaporator temperature lower than 0°C, nanorefrigerant can be beneficial. Whereas, for all condenser temperatures selected in the study, nanorefrigerant outperforms pure R600a in terms of COP.
- Total exergy destruction of the cycle reduces with addition of nanoparticles into the refrigerant. Nearly 36% reduction in exergy destruction is obtained by nanorefrigerant with 0.5% Al₂O₃ at fixed cycle temperatures. Exergy destruction is minimum with Al₂O₃/R600a when compared to pure R600a at all practical evaporator and condenser temperatures i.e. at negative evaporator temperatures and higher condenser temperatures.
- Nanorefrigerant also improves the exergy efficiency of the cycle, specifically at lower evaporator temperatures and higher condenser temperatures. Keeping condenser temperature fixed, maximum exergy efficiency enhancement of 32% is obtained by 0.2% Al₂O₃ nanoparticles.

Findings suggest that Al₂O₃/ R600a can be used as working fluid in VCRC in place of existing refrigerants. The suggested environment friendly nanorefrigerant not only enhances performance but also reduces cycle irreversibility. However, addition of nanoparticles beyond a certain concentration may adversely affect the performance as it will cause a rise in viscosity and pressure drop. Furthermore, precipitation and agglomeration of nanoparticles is a real issue that need to be addressed.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aktas, M., Dalkilic, A. S., Celen, A., Cebi, A., Mahian, O., & Wongwises, S. (2015). A theoretical comparative study on nanorefrigerant performance in a single-stage vapor-compression refrigeration cycle. *Advances in Mechanical Engineering*, 7(1), 138725.
- [2] Aktemur, C., & Öztürk, İ. T. (2022). Thermodynamic performance enhancement of booster assisted ejector expansion refrigeration systems with R1270/CuO nano-refrigerant. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 253, 115191.
- [3] Alawi, O. A., Salih, J. M., & Mallah, A. R. (2019). Thermo-physical properties effectiveness on the coefficient of performance of Al₂O₃/R141b nano-refrigerant. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*, 103, 54-61.
- [4] Ali, H. M., Generous, M. M., Ahmad, F., & Irfan, M. (2017). Experimental investigation of nucleate pool boiling heat transfer enhancement of TiO₂-water based nanofluids. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 113, 1146-1151
- [5] Baqeri, S., Akhavan-Behabadi, M. A., & Ghadimi, B. (2014). Experimental investigation of the forced convective boiling heat transfer of R-600a/oil/nanoparticle. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*, 55, 71-76.
- [6] Dey, P., & Mandal, B. K. (2020). A numerical approach to estimate the thermophysical properties and convective heat transfer characteristics of Al₂O₃/R600a nanorefrigerant. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2273, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
- [7] Dey, P., & Mandal, B. K. (2021). Performance enhancement of a shell-and-tube evaporator using Al₂O₃/R600a nanorefrigerant. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 170, 121015.
- [8] Dhamneya, A. K., Rajput, S. P. S., & Singh, A. (2018). Comparative performance analysis of ice plant test rig with TiO₂-R-134a nano refrigerant and evaporative cooled condenser. *Case studies in thermal engineering*, 11, 55-61.
- [9] Ham, J., & Cho, H. (2016). Theoretical analysis of pool boiling characteristics of Al₂O₃ nanofluid according to volume concentration and nanoparticle size. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 108, 158-171.
- [10] Henderson, K., Park, Y. G., Liu, L., & Jacobi, A. M. (2010). Flow-boiling heat transfer of R-134a-based nanofluids in a horizontal tube. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 53(5-6), 944-951.

- [11] Javadi, F. S., & Saidur, R. (2013). Energetic, economic and environmental impacts of using nanorefrigerant in domestic refrigerators in Malaysia. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 73, 335-339.
- [12] Kanoğlu, M., Çengel, Y. A., & Dinçer, İ. (2012). *Efficiency evaluation of energy systems*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- [13] Li, S., & Lu, J. (2022). A theoretical comparative study of vapor-compression refrigeration cycle using Al₂O₃ nanoparticle with low-GWP refrigerants. *Entropy*, 24(12), 1820.
- [14] Mahbulul, I. M., Saadah, A., Saidur, R., Khairul, M. A., & Kamyar, A. (2015). Thermal performance analysis of Al₂O₃/R-134a nanorefrigerant. *International Journal of heat and Mass transfer*, 85, 1034-1040.
- [15] Mahdi, Q. S., Theeb, M. A., & Saed, H. (2017). Enhancement on the performance of refrigeration system using the nano-refrigerant. *Journal of Energy and Power Engineering*, 11(4), 237-243.
- [16] Norouzipour, A., Abdollahi, A., & Afrand, M. (2019). Experimental study of the optimum size of silica nanoparticles on the pool boiling heat transfer coefficient of silicon oxide/deionized water nanofluid. *Powder Technology*, 345, 728-738.
- [17] Pak, B. C., & Cho, Y. I. (1998). Hydrodynamic and heat transfer study of dispersed fluids with submicron metallic oxide particles. *Experimental Heat Transfer an International Journal*, 11(2), 151-170.
- [18] Sajid, M. U., & Ali, H. M. (2018). Thermal conductivity of hybrid nanofluids: a critical review. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 126, 211-234.
- [19] Salehy, Y., Hoang, H. M., Cluzel, F., Leroy, Y., Delahaye, A., Fournaison, L., & Yannou, B. (2020). Energy performances assessment for sustainable design recommendations: Case study of a supermarket's refrigeration system. *Procedia CIRP*, 90, 328-333.
- [20] Sarrafzadeh Javadi, F., & Saidur, R. (2021). Thermodynamic and energy efficiency analysis of a domestic refrigerator using Al₂O₃ nano-refrigerant. *Sustainability*, 13(10), 5659.
- [21] Tazarv, S., Saffar-Avval, M., Khalvati, F., Mirzaee, E., & Mansoori, Z. (2016). Experimental investigation of saturated flow boiling heat transfer to TiO₂/R141b nanorefrigerant. *Experimental Heat Transfer*, 29(2), 188-204.
- [22] Yang, D., Sun, B., Li, H., & Fan, X. (2015). Experimental study on the heat transfer and flow characteristics of nanorefrigerants inside a corrugated tube. *International Journal of Refrigeration*, 56, 213-223.
- [23] Yilmaz, M., Cimsit, C., Keven, A., & Karaali, R. (2024). Analysis of cascade vapor compression refrigeration system using nanorefrigerants: energy, exergy, and environmental (3E). *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, 57, 104373.